
ACTIVITIES REPORT 2024

INFORMATICS
EUROPE

Informatics Europe 2024 Activities Report

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Binzmühlestrasse 14/54

8050 Zurich, Switzerland
www.informatics-europe.org
administration@informatics-europe.org

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President's Executive Summary

Dear members, colleagues, and friends,

In 2024, Informatics Europe made great strides in community building, advancing Informatics research and education, and influencing policies at the European level. A series of milestones reaffirm our collective impact and commitment to the future of Informatics.

Guided by our [Strategic Focus Areas](#), a key success was the **EUGAIN COST Action**, which concluded with outstanding evaluations and strong recognition from the European Cooperation in Science & Technology and the community. Engaging 160+ members across 46 countries, it laid a solid foundation for gender balance in Informatics. We broadly distributed one of its key outcomes—the **Policy Recommendations for Gender Balance in Informatics**—to institutions, policymakers and stakeholders across Europe, ensuring a lasting impact.

Another major step forward was the launch of **SCHIER (Summer School on Informatics Education Research)**, a first-of-its-kind initiative supporting the growth of the Informatics education research community. Enthusiastic participation from across Europe demonstrated the pressing need for this initiative, which we aim to expand in the coming years.

This year also marked the **20th anniversary of the European Informatics Leaders Summit (ECSS)**, celebrating our progress while sparking critical discussions on the future of Informatics. ECSS 2024 brought together experts to debate topics such as interdisciplinarity and sustainability in research, and AI in Informatics education and professional practice. These discussions are shaping upcoming publications that will further support our community. Meanwhile, the [Outcomes Summary](#) in this document highlights major studies, reports and policy recommendations from 2024 that continue to drive our work forward.

We remain committed to **empowering European Informatics research**. IE working groups facilitated partnerships and initiated **EU-funded projects**. Our support for early-career researchers and excellent research was again visible through the Best Dissertation **Award**, while the IE **Department Evaluation Service** contributed to enhancing members' performance and strategic development.

Our **Informatics Higher Education Data Portal** expanded further and gained international recognition in the **Stanford AI Index Report 2024**. Now covering 24 European countries, our portal remains a valuable tool for research and policy-making.

Membership growth continues to strengthen our network. In 2024, we welcomed **10 new member institutions**, bringing our total to **181 institutions across 33 countries**, representing over 50,000 Informatics researchers and educators—a testament to our mission's growing impact.

Looking ahead, Informatics Europe remains committed to pan-European collaboration, strategic leadership, and community support to policymakers. I extend my deepest gratitude to our members, working groups, and partners—together, we continue to drive progress, innovation, and collective impact.

Jean-Marc Jézéquel

President, Informatics Europe

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Introduction

In 2024, Informatics Europe continued to support and empower its members in advancing the quality and societal impact of Informatics research and education across Europe. Through our working groups (WG), strategic initiatives, and community engagement, we fostered collaboration, provided key resources, facilitated discussions, and supported policymaking on critical topics shaping the field.

2024 marked the 20th anniversary of the first European Informatics Leaders Summit (ECSS), which laid the foundation for the creation of Informatics Europe, with the association's bylaws approved the following year. This milestone provided an opportunity to reflect on two decades of progress while planning the future with renewed energy.

Informatics Europe is led by a Board of Directors, composed of academic leaders from institutions across Europe, and supported by a dedicated office team that manages daily operations, membership, and communications (details in the [Organizational Structure Annex](#)).

Strategic Focus Areas

This section highlights our key initiatives and achievements from 2024, showcasing the collective impact of our community.

Education

- Informatics in School: continued contribution to the **I4All coalition**. Key coalition activities included supporting the European Commission's expert group on informatics education, expanding efforts to empower informatics teachers, and engaging in discussions on the use of generative AI in education.
- **SCHIER (Summer School on Informatics Education Research)** launched in September, chaired by **Enrico Nardelli**, sponsored by IBM Research and joined by almost 40 participants from over 20 universities across Europe and beyond.
- Continued collaboration for the annual conference on Innovation and Technology in Informatics Education (**ITiCSE**), with **Viola Lonati** as the new IE representative in the steering committee.
- Organized the **ECSS Workshop**, focused on **AI in Informatics Education and Professional Practice**, exploring the role of AI in curricula and its implications for the profession. This session was chaired by **Pekka Orponen**, **Manuel Caro** and **Heri Ramampiaro** with the support of representatives of Informatics Europe's National Informatics Associations (NIAs).
- **Education Research WG**, under the leadership of **Jan Vahrenhold** and **Michael Kölling**, focused on the following key initiatives:
 - Participation in the **EC's Expert Group** to develop guidelines for high-quality Informatics education, represented by Enrico Nardelli.
 - Networking, knowledge exchange, and **empowerment of European Research on Data Literacy**.
 - **"Academia-Industry collaboration in Higher Education" workshop** organised at ECSS 2024; related report in progress.

- Ongoing exploration of **Data Science Education standards & recommendations** in collaboration with the Federation of European National Statistical Societies (FEnStat) and the European Association for Data Science (EuADS).

Research

- Organized the **Early Career Researchers Workshop** at ECSS 2024, chaired by **Dimka Karastoyanova** and **Irene Vanderfeesten**.
- Elaborated the **Review of the IE Research Evaluation Report**, published in 2025, under the leadership of **Pekka Orponen** and **Manuel Caro** and supported by the representatives of Informatics Europe's National Informatics Associations (NIAs).
- 2nd edition of the **Best Dissertation Award, sponsored by Springer**, was awarded to **Tobias Röddiger**, Department of Informatics, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (Germany) with the dissertation "Earables: Wearable Computing on the Ears". Apart from the winner, two runners-up were selected by the Award Committee chaired by **Dimka Karastoyanova** and **Harald Gall: Tim Quatmann**, Department of Computer Science, RWTH Aachen University (Germany) with the dissertation "Verification of Multi-Objective Markov Models"; **Michael Sammler**, Saarland University and Max Planck Institute for Software Systems (Germany), with the dissertation "Automated and Foundational Verification of Low-Level Programs".

Diversity & Inclusion

Led by **Simona Motogna** as chair of the WG and **Elisabetta Di Nitto** as Board member representative, IE pursued several Diversity & Inclusion initiatives:

- **Successful closure of the COST Action European Network for Gender Balance in Informatics (EUGAIN)**, with valuable outcomes, excellent ratings from evaluators and a network featuring more than 160 members from 46 countries, including 5 non-European ones. Informatics Europe was the main proposer and Grant Holder of this Action, where most of the management team came from IE Women in Research WG (now D&I WG), including its chair **Letizia Jaccheri** and vice-chair **Barbora Buhnova**.
- Contributed and disseminated first results of the **Erasmus+ Inclusion4EU project**, where IE is a partner.
- The **9th Edition of the Minerva Informatics Equality Award, sponsored by Google**, was awarded to the "International Women's Degree Programme in Computer Science" at Hochschule Bremen – City University of Applied Sciences, Germany. The selection was made by the Award Committee, chaired by **Antinisca Di Marco** and supported by **Lenuta Alboaie**.
- Organized the "**Cultivating Diversity: Integrating Inclusiveness into Informatics Education**" **workshop** during ECSS, together with Dymna O'Sullivan.
- Conducted a survey and published the report "Survey about diversity and inclusion initiatives", a **mapping study on diversity initiatives and artefacts** in university Informatics departments.

Green ICT

Chaired by **Marco Aiello**, the Green ICT WG focused on:

- Coordinating a **COST Action submission**, submitted in October.

- Organizing the **“Green ICT and ICT for Green” workshop at ECSS 2024**.
- Developing a **white paper on Green ICT** (in progress).

Ethics

- Networking, knowledge exchange, and **empowerment of European Research on the Principles of Humanistic Innovation**.

Data Gathering, Analysis & Reporting

While data gathering is mainly coordinated by IE Office (**Svetlana Tikhonenko**), **Přemek Brada** chaired the Data Analysis & Reporting WG (21 members). Highlights in this area included:

- Informatics Europe Higher Education Data Portal was featured in **Stanford HAI’s AI Index Report 2024** and enables the recognition of Informatics Europe by the **European Commission (DG GROW)** as a **key stakeholder** in Informatics higher education statistics.
- A joint report with the **ACM Europe Council on Bachelor’s Informatics Student Retention** is in progress.
- A **new country** (Sweden) was added to the **Higher Education Data Portal** during its annual update. This unique portal currently features Informatics HE statistics covering 24 European countries across 13 years, a joint effort of more than 60 colleagues throughout Europe.

Community Empowerment

- **20th anniversary of our European Informatics Leaders Summit (ECSS)**, with **discussions on key topics** such as interdisciplinarity and sustainability in research groups and departments, green ICT, cultivating diversity, industry-academia collaboration or AI in Informatics Education **while reflecting on the past and future of Informatics in Europe**. Several **reports are in progress** as a result of ECSS discussions, including:
 - Research Evaluation Guidelines.
 - Best Practices in Industry-Academia Collaboration.
 - Responsible AI in Informatics Education.
- Organized the 6th cohort of the **Academic Leadership Online Course**, joined by 10 participants from 9 institutions.
- Began the preparatory work for the **Department Evaluation service** to an IE-member department in Italy, with completion scheduled for the first half of 2025.
- Networking, knowledge exchange, and **empowerment of European Research on mental health and well-being** challenges throughout the Informatics academic journey.

Membership Growth & Community Engagement

Reflecting our ongoing outreach efforts, IE welcomed **10 new member institutions** this year while strengthening ties with existing members. Led by IE office staff and strongly supported by **Jean-Marc Jézéquel** and **Kim Mens**, some of these activities include:

- Direct engagement with the **top 100 European academic institutions** and **top 3 national institutions**, as well as **30 multinational corporations**.
- Emails to over **300 additional potential academic members**, followed by online introduction sessions.

- Best practice and policy recommendations **physical booklets distributed to all IE members.**
- Reinforced **communication** with revamped websites, new brochures and additional dissemination on social media.
- **20 active leads** as of year-end.

As a result, our membership at the end of 2024 includes **181 institutions across 33 countries**, representing more than **50,000 researchers** in the Informatics community.

Outcomes summary

Key reports and resources based on the work of our working groups, strategic initiatives, and community discussions in 2024 are listed in this section with direct hyperlinks:

Policy Recommendations

- [EUGAIN Booklet "Policy Recommendations for Gender Balance in Informatics"](#)
- [Feedback on the Interim Evaluation of Horizon Europe and FP10](#)

Reports

- [Inclusion4EU - Existing Competencies in the Teaching of Inclusive Design in Informatics programmes](#)
- [Inclusion4EU - The Bright Side of Design: Processes that Can Lead to the Inclusion of Users](#)
- [Inclusion4EU - The Dark Side of Design: Processes that Can Lead to the Exclusion of Users](#)
- [Artificial Intelligence \(AI\) Index Report 2024](#)
- [Survey about Diversity and Inclusion Initiatives](#)
- [EUGAIN Booklet: Best Practices From Bachelor/Master Studies to Ph.D.](#)
- [Summary of SCHIER 2024](#)
- [Summary of the 6th cohort of the Online Academic Leadership Development Course](#)
- [2024 Minerva Informatics Equality Award - The International Women's Degree Programme in Computer Science at Hochschule Bremen – City University of Applied Sciences, Germany.](#)
- [2024 Best Dissertation Award](#)
 - Winner: [“Earables: Wearable Computing on the Ears”](#) by Tobias Röddiger
 - Runner-up: [“Verification of Multi-Objective Markov Models”](#) by Tim Quatmann
 - Runner-up: [“Automated and Foundational Verification of Low-Level Programs”](#) by Michael Sammler
- [ECSS 2024 Highlights, Presentations and Closing Statements](#)

Data

- [2022-2023 academic year statistics and new country \(Sweden\) in the IE HE Data Portal](#)

[IE Bulletins](#) have been distributed to registered members and non-members, along with [News & Announcements](#) published on our [website](#) and shared via social media, to keep our community informed of ongoing activities.

Conclusion & Future Outlook

In 2024, IE fostered dialogue, provided valuable resources, and strengthened the community's ability to shape the future of Informatics through working groups, strategic collaborations, and dedicated events. The 20th anniversary of ECSS served as a key moment to reflect on past achievements and drive future initiatives, with several reports now in progress.

Annex - Organizational Structure

Board of Directors (2024)

- **Jean-Marc Jézéquel** (President) – IRISA/University of Rennes
- **Marco Aiello** (Vice President, Green ICT) – University of Stuttgart
- **Kim Mens** (Vice President, Membership) – Université catholique de Louvain
- **Elisabetta Di Nitto** (Treasurer, Diversity & Inclusion) – Politecnico di Milano
- **Lenuta Alboaie** (Industry Engagement) – Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iași
- **Přemek Brada** (Data Analysis & Reporting) – University of West Bohemia
- **Manuel Carro** (Open Science) – UPM/IMDEA
- **Harald Gall** (Department Evaluation) – University of Zurich
- **Gert Jervan** (Industry Engagement) – Tallinn University of Technology
- **Dimka Karastoyanova** (Early Career Researchers) – University of Groningen
- **Michael Kölling** (Education) – King's College London
- **Dympna O'Sullivan** (Ethics) – TU Dublin
- **Pekka Orponen** (National Informatics Associations Relations) – Aalto University
- **Heri Ramampiaro** (National Informatics Associations Relations) – NTNU
- **Jan Vahrenhold** (Education) – University of Münster
- **Enrico Nardelli** (SCHIER) - Università di Roma "Tor Vergata" (ex-officio, Past President)
- **Nuria Anguera** (IE Office; ex-officio, Executive Director)

Informatics Europe Office

- **Nuria Anguera** – Executive Director
- **Kit Wan Chui** – Communications & Admin
- **Marimar Rodriguez** – Admin & Accounting (as of January 14, 2024)
- **Svetlana Tikhonenko** – Web, Data & Analysis

Working Groups Members

- <https://www.informatics-europe.org/join-us/active-working-groups.html>

For enquiries and feedback about this report,
please contact administration@informatics-europe.org

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